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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MAB	mAKE Advisory Board
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PMB	Project Management Board
PU	Public
RE	Restricted
R&I	Research & Innovation
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This Project Handbook describes the internal procedures of the mAkE consortium in terms of management structures, communication and collaboration as well as quality control measures. It also defines the way the partners are dealing with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), especially considering ethical issues related to personal data collection, analysis and storage (see also Deliverable D9.1, D9.2, and D9.3 on specific ethics requirements). Open source and open access are important elements of the project programme itself as well as of the consortium's RRI strategy. How we are dealing with these aspects is reflected in the open data management plan, which will be shortly addressed here and is presented in detail in D8.2.

The main target group for this deliverable is the consortium partners themselves as this handbook defines the project internal processes for securing high quality research work to be performed across a set of complementary partner institutions. It serves as a reference document for all mAkE team members including individuals joining in the project at a later stage.

Since the project is bringing together a set of diverse experts from different fields and backgrounds, a core principle guiding internal processes is open participation and flexibility. Transparency about the project status as well as risk recognition are additional principles that the project partners are committed to.

Still, in order to effectively operate in a distributed team, we have defined some procedures of how to best communicate and structure our collaboration. Regular meetings are held via web-conference as well as face-to-face. Communication is also taking place via e-mail and the project mailing list. The main tool for sharing and collaborating on documents is Google Drive. For sharing of any sensitive data, Nextcloud will be used.

The consortium is committed to producing high quality project outcomes and deliverables and thus quality control is important. Quality guidelines describe the internal peer review process, which is applied to all project deliverables. For assuring quality in our internal collaboration process short internal surveys or reflection sessions may be performed, normally in connection with project meetings. These instruments are intended for the whole group to serve as a self-reflection and self-evaluation tool about the project structures.

In terms of ethics, the consortium is following the general rules defined by the EC and commits strongly to respect the individual and their privacy at all times. Templates have been prepared for informed consent (Deliverable D9.1) as well as the exchange of primary research data amongst partners that may contain personal data from study participants. The ethics requirements also consider personal data collection, processing, and storage to be in line with the GDPR (D9.2) and the data exchange between EU and third

countries (D9.3). Raising awareness about related RRI issues is of concern for the management and is regularly stressed.

Finally, openness is a core value of the project and thus the consortium is looking into open strategies with regards to the research and innovation outcomes. This relates to software that is published under specific open licences, following and where possible contributing to open standards, as well as the research publications, which should be made openly accessible as far as possible. This handbook is understood as a living document and is updated if the need arises in order to improve the internal processes.

1. Introduction

The mAKE project promotes cooperation and strategic partnerships between digital innovation hubs (DIHs) in Africa and Europe. Its overall aim is to strengthen a EU–Africa innovation and start-up ecosystem by creating the necessary infrastructure for decentral production and collaboration as well as shared policy frameworks and educational opportunities.

Thus, mAKE strengthens existing networks of makerspaces as key drivers for local digital innovation in Africa and establishes mutual and sustainable networks with European DIHs. mAKE focuses on connecting makerspaces, as they are important actors in the local digital innovation ecosystems in both Europe and Africa, in particular in regard to digital, local manufacturing and innovation in product design and development, therefore complementing more software-oriented digitisation projects in Europe and Africa. Apart from developing common infrastructure and resources, mAKE will organise capacity-building activities to equip African makerspaces and their attached local SMEs and digital start-ups with the necessary skills to engage in innovation in hardware manufacturing, and will offer incubation, mentoring and matching activities for makers and makerspaces in Africa and Europe.

mAKE is an innovation action that aims to strengthen the capacity of makerspaces in Africa and collaboration between spaces and makers in Africa and Europe. The work is organised along 9 Work packages. Work packages 1,2,3 and 4 are the key output components of mAKE, each addressing one of the key areas identified in the concept: Financial Sustainability, Policy and Regulation, and Ecosystem Building, Education and Culture, Infrastructure and Market. Work package 1,2, and 4 each contribute to the Toolkit and the open learning materials. Work package 5 ensures the widespread communication, dissemination and exploitation of results and deliverables achieved through work packages 1,2,3 and 4. Work package 6 not only ensures the sustainable update of results in form of publication in open repositories and embedded white label solutions, it will also ensure the growth of an active, international community that will contribute to the co-creation of deliverables and ensure the growth of a vibrant network of African and European DIHs and their wider ecosystem. Work package 7 will accompany the other WPs during the whole project run-time to provide evidence for their high-quality performance and collect data to assess the

achieved and future potential impact of the project. WP8 assures that the project is completed on time, according to budget and in appropriate quality. And WP9 is responsible for overlooking the ethical requirements.

Picture 1: mAKE – alignment of work packages

The mAKE project is committed to high quality output and responsible research and innovation. Thus, this document defines a set of procedures that the consortium is committed to adhering to and to improving in the course of the project.

Openness and transparency are two of the guiding principles that the reader will see reflected in the different processes and methods described. At the same time, there is a strong awareness within the consortium related to privacy and data protection of individual citizens. These core principles underlying the research work in mAKE correspond with the practices related to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).

Section 2 below describes the management structures, including the nominees for the various boards. Section 3 is dedicated to specific quality management procedures, including communication structures and tools, the peer reviewing process for high quality deliverables as well as risk management, SWOT, and other quality assurance means. In Section 4 the technical infrastructure for communication and collaboration is presented. Section 5 presents the RRI policies and identifies the most relevant aspects for mAKE. It includes the ethical approach and guidelines that the project is following (together with deliverables D9.1, D9.2, and D9.3). In Section 6 the consortium’s strategy towards openness is described and relates to open source in terms of software as well as open access in terms of publications and other project results. Finally, Section 7 draws the conclusions that are relevant for high quality implementation of the project.

The appendix includes examples of templates mentioned throughout the document.

2. Management structure

Both the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA) specify a number of bodies for the management of the project. Though the GA and CA, being legal documents, take precedence over this handbook, the following sections specify the operational view of these bodies.

mAKE is a large-scale innovation action aiming at a wide community on a global scale, with a special focus on Europe and Africa. Therefore, the management structure and procedures work in a **flexible manner** in order to:

- Achieve integration of all consortium members and mobilise their expertise, knowledge, and networks in every stage of the project
- Efficiently coordinate the processing of the work plan in a collaborative environment
- Continuously involve contextual expertise and knowledge of relevant stakeholders from local innovation hubs and their networks

Our approach is a combination of integration and decentralisation strategies. *Integration* is achieved through the composition of a consortium with complementary skills and knowledge, the development of a joint framework, the agreement on common guidelines for co-design activities, the joint work on the platform and community development, and project workshops and meetings. The resources of all partners will be mobilised by *decentralisation of responsibilities* through the assignment of leadership for work packages and defined work package tasks with a clear task-sharing based on the different competence fields of the partners.

Picture 2: mAKE – Management Structure: responsible roles in management

The management structure defines the basic roles and responsibilities. The Coordinator (Dr. Barbara Kieslinger, ZSI) is responsible for the overall administrative actions of the project. Additional ZSI staff is providing financial and administrative support to the coordinator.

GIG is the second main partner taking a leading role in management and coordination. GIG is coordinating the knowledge management of the project. This includes the management of dependencies amongst the work packages and tasks as well as the overall guidance and leadership on the project objectives and contributions to its sustainability. As WP6 Leader, GIG has also been assigned the role of Community Manager (Geraldine de Bastion), who is responsible for the coordination of the mAKE extended network. The community manager takes care of the broad visibility of the project, amongst specific stakeholder groups and will have a special interest in the exploitation and transferability of the project results.

The project managers are supported by the WP leaders in the strategic coordination of the innovation action.

2.1 Work Package (WP)

The work package (WP) is the building block of the project. The WP leader

- organizes the WP and coordinates the different tasks,
- prepares and chairs WP meetings,
- organizes the production of the results of the WP,
- represents the WP in the Project Management Board.

Each work package has been appointed a Work Package Leader who is responsible for the progress within the work package and who is supported by task leaders and other members of the consortium involved in each of the WPs. Clear responsibilities (based on the competences of each partner) are described in the Work Package Description. Current WP leaders are shown in Table 1.

Workpackage	Lead partner	Name
WP1 – Venture Building and Business Models	Greentec	Bienvenue Angui
WP2 – Hub Ecosystem and Policy Frameworks	AMN	Gertrude Mawuena Goh
WP3 – Open Education, Skills Development and Capacity Building	APSOHA	Thomas Hervé Mboa
WP4 – Distributed Manufacturing Network	Field Ready	Andrew Lamb
WP5 – Communication, Dissemination and Outreach	IAAC	Kate Armstrong

WP6 – Community Engagement and Sustainability	GIG	Geraldine de Bastion
WP7 – Evaluation and Impact Assessment	ZSI	Teresa Schaefer
WP8 – Project Management	ZSI	Barbara Kieslinger
WP9 – Ethics Requirements	ZSI	Barbara Kieslinger

Table 1: Assigned WP leaders

2.2 Project Management Board (PMB)

The project is managed through the Project Management Board (PMB). It provides the overall direction for the project, both strategic and operational. The PMB maintains the project directions and obtains advice from the Work Package Leaders, to ensure that the project meets its stated and implied goals. The PMB ultimately supervises all project management processes, including initiation, planning, execution, control, and closure of project phases. Within this framework, the Work Package Leaders coordinate the detailed planning, execution, and control of the technical tasks to meet the project's scientific and technical objectives relevant to their work packages.

The Project Management Board is responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly and makes suggestions to the General Assembly on a pending decision such as:

- Accept or reject changes to the work plan, changes in the Grant Agreement, and amendments to the Consortium Agreement
- Make changes in the Project Management structure

The PMB is chaired by the Project Coordinator and composed of the Work Package Leaders plus a representative from partners not leading a work package. The PMB is currently composed of the persons listed in Table 2 below.

Partner	Partner manager
ZSI	Barbara Kieslinger

GIG	Geraldine De Bastion
GreenTec	Bienvenue Angui
AMN	Gertrude Mawuena Goh
AOSH	Frank Landon Bantum
APSOHA	Thomas Hervé Mboa
Field Ready	Andrew Lamb
IAAC	Sara Bosch
UCT	Chris Armstrong

Table 2: Partner managers

2.3 General Assembly (GA)

At least twice a year a General Assembly (GA), consisting of the consortium members will take place. The General Assembly is obligatory for the Project Management Board, which consists of all WP leaders and partners. The goal of the GA is to ensure the smooth running of the project, the integration of each work package, and the enabling of the work in progress by setting the next tasks for the consortium members. The responsibilities of the various parties are described in more detail below. The GA will take place in connection to events hosted by consortium members or strongly connected to the project. Per year, one GA will take place in Africa, and one in Europe, should the global travel situation permit physical meetings. If travel restrictions persist due to COVID-19, the GA will be held online.

Decisions taken during the General Assembly include the content, e.g. changes in the Description of Action (DoA), finances, and intellectual property rights. This body also has the right to decide on the evolution of the partnership (e.g. entry of new partner), and the project as such (e.g. termination of the project). If needed, an extraordinary General Assembly meeting can be called at any time upon written request (including electronically via e-mail) of any Member of the Project Management Board.

2.4 mAKE Advisory Board

The mAKE Advisory Board (MAB) is a group of persons from outside the project. The MAB will be consulted for important decisions that affect the direction of research and/or are related to the adoption of the results from the mAKE project.

The MAB members are listed in Table 3. This is the status at the time of writing the deliverable, including those who have confirmed their role as MAB members. The list may potentially be extended with a few more experts.

MAB members	Affiliation
Francesca Bria	Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose at UCL
Louise Bezuidenhout	Institute for Science, Innovation and Society at the University of Oxford
Francesco Cingolani	Volumes
Tayo Akinyemi	AfriLabs
Rebecca Enochong	AppsTech
Peter Troxler	Hogeschool Rotterdam, The Netherlands
Didier Nkurikiyimfura	Smart Arfica Secretariat

Table 3: List of MAB members

During the Kick-off meeting, it was decided that this group of external experts can still be expanded with 2-3 persons for a strategic purpose.

2.5 Consortium Agreement (CA)

Before the start of the project, a consortium agreement has been signed by all partners. It defines the specific operational procedures for the different project bodies described above. This includes, amongst other aspects, the responsibilities of the parties and their liabilities towards each other as well as the governance structure, financial provision, and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues. The consortium agreement also describes the decision-making structures and defines the General Assembly as the ultimate decision-making body.

3. Quality procedures and Code of Conduct

Quality assurance is of high priority in collaborative research, such as mAKE, and the consortium is committed to a set of quality procedures to guarantee high quality project output. Measures to ensure good quality include e.g. the definition of internal communication structures, regular internal reflections on risks, and a proper SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats Analysis) as well as a defined peer review process for any project deliverable. The detailed procedures will be described in more detail in the following sections.

3.1 Internal communication structures & procedures

Internal communication is first and foremost based on the concept of openness and transparency. An active communication strategy is implemented to establish a strong project identity in order to obtain maximum transparency for all partners involved, and to increase synergy in cooperation.

Daily communication among the WPs, the partners, etc. is established mainly through

- . e-mails and a central mailing list including all project partners,
- . a WhatsApp group for quick communication across teams and partners,
- . a shared Google drive folder for daily collaboration
- . a project space hosted at the ZSI (Nextcloud) for internal exchange and online storage of all documents that contain any sensitive data; <https://cloud2.zsi.at>,
- . web-conferencing (Zoom) for regular online meetings,
- . easily accessible online collaboration tools, such as Jamboard, etc.
- . face-to-face communication (during physical project meetings).

The consortium partners meet approximately every three to four months face-to-face (at synchronisation points) to coordinate the progress. Each month, at least one virtual consortium meeting takes place via web-conferencing. These meetings ensure internal communication among partners, allow the WP Leaders/thematic leaders to coordinate the various tasks, and report the progress of work to the team members.

During the meeting “live minutes” will be produced and are made accessible to all partners, to view at a later time. Each team reports about the latest updates before a meeting in a shared document, all participants are invited to get an update before the meeting starts and the most relevant issues are then discussed during the meetings. The minutes, which do not include any sensitive information, are available in the shared online project folder.

In addition to these virtual consortium meetings, thematic groups according to the WPs have started to emerge during the kick-off meeting and virtual meetings are organised by these working groups. Similar to the consortium meeting notes and recordings are available on Google drive and each member of the consortium is invited to attend any of these meeting.

WP6 is taking a lead on coordinating co-creation activities throughout the project. Co-creation is an important methodological aspect of this project and GIG as the leading partner will assure that involvement in the co-creation process will be made as easy as possible for all stakeholders. E.g., we will make sure that low bandwidth and asynchronous collaboration will be facilitated.

3.2 External communication structures & procedures

The communication strategy also aims to effectively communicate with parties outside the consortium, especially since mAKE is an Innovation Action that aims at reaching and engaging a broad audience to create sustainable impact.

Stakeholders will be addressed via the community engagement and communications strategy, which is coordinated in a collaborative effort by WP5 and WP6. Details for the external communication in terms of procedures and material will be elaborated and aligned across these WPs. Basically, different communication options will be elaborated for the different target groups.

3.3. Quality of (non-) deliverables and peer reviews

A **peer-review process** for the mAKE project is set up in order to obtain and guarantee the quality of the deliverables (documentation, reports, prototypes, etc.) that will be produced during the course of the project and delivered to the European Commission, offered to the mAKE stakeholders and more globally to the general public. This section describes standards for the mAKE deliverables and presents the peer-review procedure. A checklist for the deliverables and a template for peer-review reports are given in Appendices to this document.

3.3.1 Deliverables

mAke deliverables serve different purposes. They are a communication means within the consortium and communication with other people outside the consortium. They are aimed at transferring the know-how to exploit the results and knowledge generated by the project. Deliverables should be written with their target readers in mind. They should be concise and easy to follow. The readability of a document is a vital ingredient for its success. WP5 is supporting a variety of presentation formats for the project communication and outcomes to make sure that target groups are appropriately addressed.

mAke deliverables are identified in the Description of Action as either reports or demonstrators/other. Demonstrators typically comprise software as pilots, prototypes, or plan designs. They should be supported by a short documentation report.

The following general structure should be followed for deliverables in report format. This structure is also provided in the deliverable template of the project:

- Cover page
- Amendment History
- List of Authors/Contributors
- Table of Contents
- Abbreviations/Acronyms
- Executive summary
- Introductory part
- Core part
- References
- Annexes (optional)

Annex I includes a checklist that should serve as a guideline when preparing a deliverable. A mAke deliverable may be comprised of one or more volumes and may consist of the following parts:

- The *Main part* is the part that summarises the results for high-level executives, technical managers and experts with decision-making competence. It is typically one document and may contain Appendices
- *Annexes* are optional and have detailed technical information for experts and implementers. They are added to the main part at the end of the document.

Project deliverables may be classified according to different confidentiality levels, such as public (PU), restricted (RE) or confidential (CO). Following an open access strategy, which the project partners are committed to, all mAke deliverables have been classified as PU regarding their dissemination level in the

DoA. PU means completely public access and thus, all deliverables will be made available on the project website and/or specific open repositories, such as Zenodo. In the case consortium members want to change the level of confidentiality of any of the deliverables this requires a decision by the General Assembly and needs to be convincingly argued.

In the following, steps to be taken for publishing a deliverable are listed:

1. These parts form the basis for the deliverable
 - Title and description of the project deliverables
 - The name(s) of the deliverables editor(s)
 - The deliverable history including names(s) of contributors and internal reviewer(s) in charge of the peer review for the deliverable
2. The people appointed to generate parts of the Deliverable – the authors – provide their contribution to the editor.
3. The editor(s) prepare draft 0.1 of the Deliverable by assembling and integrating all contributions. This draft is discussed with all authors. It is recommended to create the drafts directly in the shared drive and involve the internal reviewers already at this stage.
4. When the editors and the authors are satisfied with the results achieved, the editor issues draft 1.0 and puts it on the mAKE shared drive and sends a note to the consortium.
5. They inform the internal reviewers and ask for a quality check, opinions and constructive comments within a defined deadline (normally one week).
6. The editor deals with all the comments and problems raised, if necessary with the help of the authors. This is a critical phase due to the many interactions involved. It may be necessary to have a meeting (physical, audio- or video conference) in order to speed up the process for reaching a consensus on the amendments.
7. The editor prepares draft 2.0, puts it on the mAKE shared drive and informs the project manager (Dr. Barbara Kieslinger) and the whole consortium that the deliverable has reached final status and can be submitted to the EC and the reviewers.
8. The deliverable is submitted to the EC portal only by the project manager.

3.3.2 Peer review process

One of the feasible means to enhance the quality of the project deliverables is an internal peer review system. mAKE deliverables shall be evaluated by 2–3 reviewers to gather diversified and balanced viewpoints. Deliverables can be reviewed by members of the core project team or colleagues from the partner institutions as well as invited external experts, for example Advisory Board members. Peer reviewers should be nominated by the editor(s) at least 3 weeks before the due date of the deliverable and communicated to the consortium. Nominated peer reviewers can turn down the invitation

with clear justification (e.g. lack of expertise, lack of time) and would thus be requested to nominate another candidate.

Consented peer reviewers are required to produce peer review feedback within 7–10 days after receiving the deliverable from the editor. In case of any expected delay, peer reviewers should notify the editor and the project manager immediately. During the review process, peer reviewers are encouraged to discuss the problems identified in the deliverable with the main author/editor. Peer reviewers are advised to pay particular attention to the following points:

- Is the deliverable aligned with the objectives of the project and relevant work packages?
- Does the deliverable make a significant contribution to the project or not?
- Is the content of the deliverable focused on the intended purpose? Is the content of the deliverable presented in a precise and to-the-point manner?
- Is the length of the deliverable justified? Are there superfluous or irrelevant parts that should be deleted? Are there overlong parts that should be shortened? Are there any parts that are written in flowery language and/or that are unspecific or redundant?
- Are there many grammatical errors and/or typographical errors and/or incomprehensive sentences? Specifically, clear annotations indicating errors and suggested corrections are very helpful for the authors of the deliverable. The annotated deliverable may be sent back to the editor/authors via email together with the peer review report.
- Does the deliverable require substantial revision or rewriting? If yes, it will facilitate the revision process if some concrete suggestions on how to improve the deliverable are given.

Peer review results are described in a peer review report/e-mail (see Annex III), which contains the following information:

- Basic information about the deliverable, author and peer reviewer
- Comments on the length and content of the deliverable
- Major strengths and weaknesses of the deliverable
- Review summary

If minor or substantial revisions are necessary, editors/authors of the deliverable should make changes and produce the final version of the deliverable before the due submission date. The final responsibility for the content of the deliverable remains with the editor and authors and it is thus their final decision about how to address and integrate the feedback from the peer reviewers. The review reports will be made available internally for the consortium only.

Picture 3: Peer review process

3.3.3 Non-deliverables

For non-deliverables, such as publications and dissemination material, the procedure for deliverables will be used where applicable and with a timeline that fits the material.

Since there are many types of material, this handbook cannot provide details for all cases. We distinguish the following broad categories of material.

- Dissemination material (flyer, website, leaflets, popular science publications, etc.)
Default reviewers are the WP5 and WP6 leaders, supported by the project manager.
- Scientific publication or conference presentation reviewed by one or more team members according to focus and contributions.

3.4 Internal surveys

mAKE is committed to a **continuous improvement process** on the project management level. In addition to open and transparent communication and decision-making, the project management uses anonymous surveys for specific input on process management, risks and critical issues. These surveys are kept brief to ensure broad participation by each project member. The survey is distributed according to needs (no pre-defined schedule), but at least once a year (ideally before a GA meeting) to cover the following:

- *Project management.* In this section, participants are asked to share their positive and negative observations about the project management processes.
- *Current topics.* The second section focuses on topics that are currently important within the project. This can range from collaboration infrastructure to satisfaction about certain results, or specific WP-level topics. A recurring topic will be questions regarding Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in order to sensitise project partners for the most relevant aspects of RRI for mAKE.

- *Expectations and perceived risks.* The third section focuses on the future and asks participants to share their perception about risks and expectations.

An essential element of this survey process is that the results are discussed and reflected upon in the consortium, preferably during a face-to-face meeting. This allows for reacting to arising issues quickly and addressing them collaboratively, e.g., by adapting the agenda.

3.5 Risk management

As stated above, internal surveys and discussions are used to check perceived concerns and risks by all consortium partners. In addition, the updates that each WP leader gives during the monthly meetings offer time and space to address also possible risks, deviations or corrective actions to be reported to the project management.

The basic risk management methodology to be followed in the project consists of four subsequent steps:

- Risk identification – areas of potential risk are identified and classified.
- Risk quantification – the probability of events is determined and the consequences associated with their occurrence are examined.
- Risk response – methods are produced to reduce or control the risk, e.g. switch to alternative technologies.
- Risk control and report – lessons learnt are documented.

Risks with medium or high probability and severe impact are handled with particular caution during the project. At this point, it is expected that the project safely achieves its expected results. This is also supported by the preliminary risk analysis as outlined in the Description of Action. Normal project risks are managed via “good-practice” project management and rely on the experience from the successful projects that the partners have been performing. The close supervision and tight control both by the project management and by the various Boards ensure that results are available in time and with adequate quality.

Description of risk	Work package(s)	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Lack of ability to travel or do on site work in a post Corona world	WP8, WP6, WP3, WP2, WP1	Hold online co-creation and consortium meetings. The network partners are experienced in decentral collaboration and online events, trainings and workshops. While face-to-face interactions are preferred, most of the activities in the work plan have been designed in a way to be conducted online. The planned offline gatherings to connect communities will in our estimation require equal amounts of planning time should they need to take place online.
Lack of ability to integrate existing technologies/data	WP3, WP4	Workarounds ranging from manual integration to automated processes (macros, cron jobs) or source system alterations will be considered as appropriate. Careful coordination between tasks and work packages in advance of system selection, combined with open innovation practices so stakeholders can see potential issues in advance, will help to reduce the need for workarounds.
Low local visibility of the project for targeted groups, including policy makers	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	Consortium partners are well connected in the local communities and have already gained visibility. Additionally, local co-operations will be considered with specific makerspaces, some of which have already expressed their interest through Letters of Interest; specific targeted dissemination material will be provided. Specific events for policy makers will be organised.
No suitable participants for matchmaking activities are found, either on European or African side	WP1	Apart from engaging to the extensive networks of the consortium partners, other communities and networks will be tapped into.
Competition with other initiatives aiming at policy dialogues between innovators and policy makers	WP2, WP5	Collaboration with other projects existing such as #i4Policy, AfriLabs and new projects funded through Horizon2020. The consortium members have long standing working relationships with these and other organisations working in this field in Africa and Europe and have been supporting them through their events, communication and outreach activities or direct collaboration.
Distributed Manufacturing Infrastructures not usable for potential clients	WP4	Extensive UX research – with the added benefit of involving potential clients early on will ensure usability considerations are taken into account during design. Internet access in most DIHs is good, even if only through cellular data network.

Legal and ethical restrictions for sharing of business models	WP4	WP4 will look very closely into the legal and ethical aspects and provide strategies on how to deal with them on a global scale; different options might have to be considered concerning specific country demands.
Keeping a balance between business developers' and maker communities' interest	WP1, WP3, WP4, WP8	Stakeholders from both sides were involved in the writing of this proposal from the beginning, and especially in designing the Work Packages. We think there is a strong will to work together to support the development of new business models based on circular and green economies. However, arising problems will be closely monitored and hopefully solved via mediation procedures in the consortium and the Work Packages.
Co--creation sessions drive project into different directions, more efforts needed than originally planned	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6	The consortium will keep the necessary flexibility to make adaptations and shifting priorities to a limited extent. The work plan as it is designed now is flexible enough to include such shifts.
Difficulty identifying female participants for trainings resulting in low gender and diversity balance	All WPs	Many DIHs are associated with women maker groups, women in STEM or women in engineering societies who may be able to help promote participation and identify how engagement could be improved. Cultural norms can be accommodated or cultural barriers can be challenged by makerspaces, for example by loaning equipment to take home or hosting mother and daughter days to sensitise families.
High effort of translation of data, documentation, interviews, etc.	All WPs	The consortium is composed of individuals with a diverse set of language skills and will be able to manage data translation internally; in case of unexpectedly high translation efforts, a translation service will be subcontracted.
Work not delivered on time by project partners	All WPs	In case of late delivery, the timing needs to be adapted. GIG and the WP leaders will closely monitor all project activities and send out early warnings.

Table 4: mAKE critical tasks

At the kick-off meeting, additional information related to risks has been performed. All partners were asked to reflect on what they expect from the project. The following two images summarise on the one hand the dreams and expectations and on the other hand the fears and risks associated with the project. The Project Management Board will follow up on these aspects and reflect on contingencies should any of the identified risks, or emerging risks, start having an influence on the activities' progress.

Picture 4: Dreams/Opportunities and Fears/Risks for mAKE

In the course of the project, management is responsible for close monitoring of the overall progress and risk identification. Risk identification is however also collaboratively encouraged as part of reflective sessions during the project meetings. Early communication of risks is encouraged as well as discussions, in order to achieve a profound understanding of risks. The project management promotes an open communication culture to openly discuss any issues arising.

3.6 SWOT

A mid-term analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) of the project is planned for the mid-term of the project. This will be done during a plenary meeting and is to be used to refocus, if needed, the project in the second half of the project.

The SWOT analysis is a structured planning method to evaluate the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats of a particular undertaking, be it for a policy or programme, a project, or product or for an organisation or individual. It is generally considered to be a simple and useful tool for analysing project objectives by identifying the internal and external factors that are favourable and unfavourable to achieving that objective. Strengths and weaknesses are regarded as internal to the project while opportunities and threats generally relate to external factors.

Strengths can be seen as characteristics of the project that give it an advantage over others while weaknesses are regarded as characteristics that place the team at a disadvantage relative to others. Opportunities comprise elements that the project could exploit to its advantage whilst threats include elements in the environment that could cause trouble for the project.

Question to be answered during the SWOT analysis comprise:

Strengths (S):

- What do we do well? What are our assets?
- What advantages does the project have? What do we do better than anyone else? What unique resources can we draw upon that others can't?
- What are our core competencies? What is the Unique Selling Proposition (USP)?
- What do other people see as our strengths?

Weaknesses (W):

- What could we improve? What can we do better?
- What should we avoid?
- Where do we lack resources?
- Which factors minimise the outcome?
- What are external people likely to see as weaknesses?

Opportunities (O):

- Which good opportunities can we spot? What are the emerging political and social opportunities?
- What interesting trends are we aware of? What are the economic trends that benefit us?
- What new needs of PES and other future users could we meet?

Threats (T):

- What obstacles do we face?
- Where are we vulnerable?
- Could any of our weaknesses seriously threaten our results? What are the negative political and social trends?

To develop strategies that take into account the SWOT profile, a matrix can be constructed. The SWOT matrix (see below) includes strategies that make the best use of strengths and opportunities and minimise weaknesses and threats. SO-Strategies pursue opportunities that are a good fit for the strengths. WO-Strategies overcome weaknesses to pursue opportunities. ST-Strategies identify ways in which the project can use its strengths to reduce its vulnerability to external threats. WT-Strategies establish a defensive plan to prevent the weaknesses from making it highly susceptible to external threats.

SWOT Matrix	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	SO-Strategies	WO-Strategies
Threats	ST-Strategies	WT-Strategies

Picture 5: SWOT Matrix

After the first matrix has been drawn from the answers by the consortium, the following questions should be answered during the discussion and establishment of the project strategy:

- How to make best use of strengths and opportunities?
- How to best minimise weaknesses by making best use of opportunities?
- How to make best use of strengths by reducing risk of threats?
- How to best minimise weaknesses even with the expected threats?

While SWOT can be a good complementary tool for analysing the project and redefining strategy, it also has several blind spots. These comprise, for instance, that SWOT is a linear analysis and an expert's or group's monophonic analysis. In the case of the mAkE project some external views, e.g. from the Advisory Board or other stakeholders would give an important complementary interpretation of the project development. Overall, SWOT is an easily usable tool that provides quick access to the positive and negative aspects of a project and its environment and seems appropriate for the mAkE project to be performed mid-term.

3.7 Project templates

mAkE intends to use a consistent 'project style'. This is implemented by providing templates for deliverables and reports, presentations, posters, and other dissemination and communication material. More project-style templates can be produced by the communication and outreach team when needed.

All available project style templates are available in different formats on the shared workspace.

4 Tools and collaboration infrastructure

While the previous section was concerned with the processes of communication and collaboration there is also a technical side to this, and a number of technical tools are used to provide the mAKE collaboration infrastructure. It consists of several pieces:

- **mAKE mailing list** is used for project-wide asynchronous communication. The address of the mailing list is: make@lists.zsi.at
- **WhatsApp** for ad-hoc communication to the whole team (as well as to different subgroups and individual team members, if needed)
- **Zoom** is used for regular web conferencing (monthly meetings)
- **Google Drive** is used for sharing files and for real-time co-creation of documents https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1MMS_2F1zTovD6UT7MO2lq1GhikgabQdS
- **Nextcloud** (<https://cloud2.zsi.at>) can be used for sharing confidential, and data that needs to be protected according to data privacy regulations as defined in the **Data Management Plan**
- **e-mail and telephone** are used for bilateral communication
- **mAKE Website** (<http://www.>) is the main portal for presenting our work to the public

The choice for this collaboration structure has been made taking into consideration practical aspects as well as privacy and data protection issues related to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

5 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

5.1 What is RRI?

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) has been formulated and widely promoted as a guiding principle and policy concept by the European Commission to better align science with society and to meet the so-called grand challenges¹. It has been promoted as a cross-cutting issue within the H2020 research programme. A widely accepted definition describes RRI as “a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products” (Schomberg, 2013). Others’ definitions of RRI (c.f. Jacob et al., 2013; Owen et al., 2013) might slightly differ from Von Schomberg’s but as described by Wickson & Carey (2014) the overall common accordance is that responsible research and innovation should (1) address significant socio-ecological needs and challenges, (2) actively engage different stakeholders, (3) anticipate potential problems and assess available alternatives and reflect on underlying values and beliefs and (4) to adapt according to

¹ Health, demographic change and wellbeing; Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy; Secure, clean and efficient energy; Smart, green and integrated transport; Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials; Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies; Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens

these ideas. Generally speaking, RRI is doing science and innovation with and for society by re-imagining the science–society relationship. According to the European Commission (Jacob et al., 2013), RRI comprises the following key dimensions²:

1. **Governance:** Governance of policymakers to prevent harmful or unethical developments in research and innovation
2. **Open Access:** Open access to research results and publications to boost innovation and increase the use of scientific results
3. **Ethics:** Research must respect ethical standards and fundamental rights to respond to societal challenges
4. **Gender:** Gender equality and in a wider sense diversity
5. **Public Engagement:** Engagement of all societal actors (researchers, industry, policy makers, civil society) in a reflective research process
6. **Science education:** Enhancement of current education processes to better equip future researchers and society as a whole with the necessary competences to participate in research processes

In addition to these key dimensions, which are reflected in the European policy agendas, RRI can also be defined with regards to its process requirements which include **openness and transparency, anticipation and reflection, responsiveness and adaptive change, and diversity and inclusion**. Figure 7, which stems from the RRI-Tools project³ where the ZSI has been a core partner, shows an integrative view on these two perspectives, which complement each other.

² A different operationalisation is described by Wickson and Carew (2014) who describe RRI from a process perspective with the following quality criteria: 1. Socially relevant and Solution oriented; 2. Sustainability centered and Future scanning; 3. Diverse and Deliberative; 4. Reflexive and Responsive; 5. Rigorous and Robust; 6. Creative and Elegant; and 7. Honest and Accountable

³ <http://www.rri-tools.eu>

Picture 6: Overview of key dimensions and process requirements of RRI according to RRI-Tools project

In the following, we briefly describe the six key dimensions and how they are related to mAKE.

5.2 Governance

Among the six key dimensions of RRI, governance has a slightly different function compared to the others, as it is rather an organising and steering principle that determines the success of all other RRI dimensions. In other words, RRI relies on good governing structures for the promotion of RRI. Governance methods range from foresight techniques (scenario studies, value-sensitive design, etc.), assessment (ethical committees, needs assessment, technology assessment, etc.), agenda-setting (consultation, co-creation, etc.) to regulation (code of conduct, policies, funding guidelines, etc.).

Currently, governance of RRI is rarely seen on a project level; it is rather applied on funding level or within organisations, e.g. to call for organisation-wide RRI guidelines and policies. The **mAKE project** can be perceived as an attempt to tackle RRI on a project level. However, comprehensive RRI guidelines for projects are still missing, and thus this handbook together with the deliverables D9.1, D9.2, and D9.3 will aim at meeting this need. Also, it has to be acknowledged that governance structures need to be at least on an institutional level in order to be sustainable. On a project level, however, it makes sense to break down what RRI in the specific context means and how it can be adapted to the project particularities.

5.3 Open access

In the narrower sense, open access is about enabling or giving access to research results and publications to the public. It addresses only the final stage of research activity, the publication, and dissemination phase. With the launch of Horizon 2020, it has become mandatory to follow open access publication strategies (European Commission, 2012).

Open access, in the narrow sense, is different from open science, open innovation, and open data, although there are obvious overlaps. For instance, in contrast to open access, open science implies opening up the whole science process in real-time to the public, from choosing areas to investigate in,

formulating the research questions to choosing the methods, collecting data, and finally discussing the results. Open science means democratising science and research, usually through ICT.

When talking about open access in the context of mAKE we refer to both open access in the narrower sense and in a wider sense of open science and open data. Our project will follow an open access publication strategy but will also make data available to the public at an earlier stage where suitable (c.f. chapter 6). One of our main target groups, namely makers, work a lot with code and design, rather than scientific publications and we want to foster an open approach to sharing also for these products, while looking for new business models, based on the concept of open access. The process of opening information is however not the same for making artefacts as it is for traditional publications. There are specific platforms for sharing such as Github, GithLab, Benchling, Thingiverse, careables, etc. and we will explore how to best support and advise makers in their approach towards openness.

5.4 Ethics

The European Commission defines ethics as a key dimension of RRI as follows:

“European society is based on shared values. In order to adequately respond to societal challenges, research and innovation must respect fundamental rights and the highest ethical standards. Beyond the mandatory legal aspects, this aims to ensure increased societal relevance and acceptability of research and innovation outcomes. Ethics should not be perceived as a constraint to research and innovation, but rather as a way of ensuring high quality results.” (p.4)⁴

Ethics thereby shall not be perceived as a constraint but rather as a guiding principle to help ensure high quality outcomes and to justify decisions. This is also the case for Critical Making. A specific work package (WP6) is dedicated to legal and ethical aspects. We will deal with the three main aspects of ethics as defined by the European Commission (2015), namely 1) Research integrity and good research practice, 2) Research ethics for the protection of research objects, and 3) Societal relevance and ethical acceptability of research and innovation outcomes.

This European-centred vision of ethics is complemented by an African perspective in the case of mAKE. A complementary approach that will be explored is based on the concept “design for the pluriverse”.

Ethics further implies social justice and inclusion aspects: The widest range of societal actors and civil society shall benefit from research and innovation outcomes. In other words, products and services as a result of Research & Innovation (R&I) activities shall be acceptable and affordable for different social groups, which is also a special goal of Critical Making.

Ethics is an integral part of responsible research, from the conceptual phase to the publication of research results. The consortium of mAKE is clearly committed to showing appreciation of potential ethical issues that may arise during the course of the project and has as such defined a set of procedures on how to deal with ethics in a responsible way.

The main aspects the project is dealing with in regards to ethics are the protection of identity, privacy, obtaining informed consent, and communicating benefits and risks to the involved target groups. The

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf

activities performed in mAKE may include data collection from individuals and organisations remotely as well as on-site. In the following, we outline the basic processes of ethical compliance of the project with a general view on the scientific data collection.

Data protection and privacy

During any data collection process, data protection issues with regards to handling personal data will be addressed by the following strategies:

Participants, who volunteer to be enrolled in our activities, will be exhaustively informed so that they are able to autonomously decide whether they consent to participate or not. The purposes of the research, the procedures as well as the handling of their data (protection, storage) will be explained. For online interviews, these explanations will be a part of the initial briefing of interviewees. For face-to-face interventions, informed consent (provided in D8.1) shall be agreed upon and signed by both the study participants as well as the respective research partner.

The data exploitation will be in line with the respective national data protection acts. Since data privacy is under threat when data is traced back to individuals – they may become identifiable and the data may be abused – to mitigate this risk, we will anonymise all data. In addition, we may be dealing with data coming from traditional knowledge, such as from indigenous people. In order to ensure their fair participation through Community Based research techniques we will take advantage of the UN declaration on indigenous people, the Nagoya protocol, and related resources.

Data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, observational studies, focus groups, workshops, and other possible data gathering methods during this research will be anonymised and therefore the data cannot be traced back to the individual. Data will be stored only in anonymous forms so the identities of the participants will only be known by the research partners involved. Raw data like interview protocols and audio files will be shared within the consortium partners only after having signed the confidentiality agreement (See Annex I). Reports based on interviews, focus groups and other data gathering methods will be based on aggregated information and will comprise anonymous quotations respectively.

The collected data will be stored on password-protected servers at the partner institution responsible for data collection and analysis. The data will be used only within the project and will not be made accessible for any third party, unless anonymised. Sensitive data or personal data will not be stored after the end of the project (incl. the time for final publications) unless required by specific national legislation.

The stored data do not contain the names or addresses of participants and will be edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g. in project reports).

Communication strategy

Study participants will be made aware of the potential benefits and identified risks of participating in the project at all times.

The main means of communicating benefits and risks to the individual is the informed consent (see Deliverable D9.1). Prior to consent, each individual participant in any of the studies in mAKE will be clearly informed of its goals, its possible adverse events, and the possibility to refuse to enter or to retract at any time with no consequences. This will be done through a project information sheet or the informed consent form and it will be reinforced verbally.

In order to make sure that participants are able to recall what they agree upon when signing, the informed consent forms will be provided in the native language of the participants. In addition, the consortium partners will make sure that the informed consent is written in a language suitable for the target group(s). Different informed consents will be made available, e.g. consent of adult participants, parental consent, informed assent for children/minors.

For media material (e.g. photos, videos) produced during any of the mAKE events, a **media waiver** will be distributed to participants to make sure that participants are aware of this and agree/disagree with the production and use of such material by the project partners. A template for the waiver is provided in Annex IV of this document.

Informed consent/informed assent

As stated above informed consent/assent will be collected from all participants involved in MAKE studies. The declaration of consent forms is provided in the Deliverable D9.1.

Relevant regulations and scientific standards

The consortium is following European regulations and scientific standards to perform ethical research. The following lists some of the basic regulations and guidelines.

The mAKE project will fully respect the citizens' rights as reported by EGE and as proclaimed in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 364/01), having as its main goal to enhance and to foster the participation of European citizens to education, regardless of cultural, linguistic or social backgrounds. Regarding the personal data collected during the research, the project will make every effort to heed the rules for the protection of personal data as described in Directive 95/46/EC⁵.

In addition, the consortium is following the following European Regulations and Guidelines:

- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union:
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT>
- European Convention on Human Rights
http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf
- Horizon 2020 ethics self-assessment
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/doc/call/h2020/h2020-msca-itn-2015/1620147-h2020_-_guidance_ethics_self_assess_en.pdf
- EU Code of Conduct:
[https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018D0221\(O2\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018D0221(O2))
- European Textbook on Ethics in Research https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/textbook-on-ethics-report_en.pdf
- European data protection legislation
- RESPECT Code of Practice for Socio-Economic Research
- Code of Ethics of the International Sociological Association (ISA)

⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=URISERV%3A114012>

National and Local Regulations and Standards

In addition to the more general and EU-wide guidelines, project partners have to adhere to, and respect, national regulations, and laws as well as to research organisational ethical approval as requested by their own institutions. All partners are aware of their responsibilities in that respect and will follow the respective guidelines. It should be stressed that many partners are located outside the European Union and additional national regulations may apply.

More details about ethical issues can be found in the deliverables of WP9 (Deliverable D9.1., D9.2., and D9.3).

5.5 Gender

Gender equality generally means equal rights, opportunities, and responsibilities for both genders so that individuals can exploit and realise their full potentials independently from their sex.

Gender equality as a key dimension of RRI comprises two main aspects (European Commission, 2015), namely to strive for gender-balanced teams in research and innovation (at operational as well as at decision-making level) and the inclusion and integration of gender perspectives in research and innovation content and process. Gender analysis and gender monitoring throughout the project shall aim at looking at both aspects of gender equality, at the human capital dimension (where possible, apart from institutional conditions), and the research aspect of gender (Föger et al., 2016).

In mAkE gender is mostly relevant when it comes to internal processes, such as the composition of project teams, of work package leaders, of the advisory group, the use of gender-sensitive language, and the awareness of producing gender-sensitive content. In line with the Toolkit on Gender in EU-funded research (European Commission, 2009) mAkE will strive at doing gender-sensitive innovation. Particularly in the following project steps gender has to be addressed and taken into account:

- Project design and methodology: we will make sure that for any of our approaches in co-design and other engagement activities, we will aim at representative data in the sense that different gender perspectives will be described, where relevant.
- Project implementation: Data-collection tools such as questionnaires, interview guidelines, etc. need to be gender-sensitive and use gender-neutral language, and have to allow for differentiation between gender perspectives. In the evaluation data analysis, we will particularly pay attention to whether there are differences between males and females, for instance, in terms of artefacts that are produced, in terms of communicating and sharing, etc.
- Dissemination phase – reporting of data: We will use gender-neutral language in our publications. Furthermore, we will sensitively decide which visual materials to use. In addition, we will aim at publishing gender-specific results.

5.6 Education

Science education under the RRI umbrella is meant to meet several objectives (European Commission, 2015; Föger et al., 2016):

- (1) To empower the society to critically reflect and to improve on their skills to be able to challenge research, thus to make them “science-literate” (in this sense, there is a great overlap with the key dimension of public engagement)
- (2) To enhance future researchers and other societal actors to become good RRI actors
- (3) To make science attractive to children and teenagers with the purpose to promote science careers, especially in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics)
- (4) To close the gap between science and education. There is still a significant distance between the two areas.

Co-creation and co-design are regarded as possible empowering methods as they enable participants to shape the development of certain technologies or services and support creative collaboration across stakeholders. mAKE has a strong commitment to co-creation processes across the various activities and this process is overall supported by WP6. In mAKE training activities are especially foreseen in WP3 activities. They are targeted at young entrepreneurs and students related to design & arts, engineering, etc., and aim to familiarise them with ethical and technical maker skills and entrepreneurial aspects. Also, the maker spaces involved in the mAKE project regularly offer educational activities to young people and schools as the maker movement has started to get attention from schools and educational authorities. Partners will only target people above 18 with project activities.

5.7 Public Engagement

In recent years, science communication has moved from the one-way-communication approach to basically informing the general public towards public engagement, which means more elaborate and active involvement of citizens leading to collaboration and empowerment.

There is a vast range of tools and methods with different levels of participation available, e.g. public consultations, public deliberations for decision making, public participation in R&I processes, Citizen Science, etc. The goal of opening up research and innovation processes to the public is to better meet the values, needs, and expectations of society and thus to improve R&I and to find solutions to the so-called grand challenges that society is facing (Cagnin, Amanatidou, & Keenan, 2012).

Thus, realising this key dimension of RRI is an important goal in mAKE and two work packages are jointly working together to reach high quality public engagement. WP5 and WP6 are closely working on a joint strategy and have created a working team at the kick-off meeting to jointly define and execute the engagement and communication strategy of the project.

5.8 RRI management in mAKE

The notion of Responsible Research and Innovation does not offer a checklist or one universal guideline on how to do RRI. It is also not in the spirit of RRI to have such a set of measures, as RRI is rather perceived as a process that requires continuous questioning and reflection. Thus, mechanisms have to be installed and embedded in the project by work packages 7, 8 and 9 to stimulate the reflection of the consortium and to keep these alive throughout the lifetime of the project.

We would like to point out that not all key dimensions are equally relevant for mAKE as can be inferred from the discussion above. In the following, we will therefore concentrate on these key dimensions which will be dealt with in more detail. However, also the remaining dimensions shall remain in our mindsets as we would like to continuously stimulate reflection and discussion on RRI.

In order to stimulate reflection and deliberation on Responsible research and innovation and to keep these alive we have foreseen several instruments:

- **Ethical and legal questionnaire:** a questionnaire addressing specific ethical and legal aspects has been distributed to all project partners at the beginning of the project. Questions range from the data that is being collected and stored by project partners to the data being collected to the compliance of the platform with the GDPR as well as data subjects' rights. This questionnaire especially informs the deliverables D9.1 and D9.2 and particularly the data management plan (D8.2).

- **RRI Self-Reflection-Tool:** The RRI-Tools project has developed the so-called “RRI Self-Reflection-Tool”. It is an online tool for different stakeholder groups and for people with different levels of knowledge on RRI. The tool is meant to comprise food for thought and to sensitise for RRI and to stimulate reflection on RRI key dimensions and process requirements. Participants can choose which questions they would like to reflect upon (since not all of them will be relevant) and receive suggestions at the end on how to further improve in terms of RRI. Further resources such as best practice examples, tools or literature will be recommended. In mAKE we will invite the project partners to regularly make use of the Self-Reflection –Tool.

To summarise, the main instruments for implementing RRI are the following:

- ethical guidelines, including forms for informed consent, code of conduct, and confidentiality agreement
- an open data management plan
- RRI self-assessment tool

6 Open access and open research data

The project firmly believes in openness to be a major factor for innovation and this was also one of the main motivations for mAKE, which promotes open hardware. Openness has many facets. The most important ones for the mAKE consortium are, following Carlos Moedas’s (European Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation) strategy of the 3 Os, Open Science, Open Innovation and Open Data⁶:

- **Open project collaboration.** All partners are committed to developing (working) relationships with external partners for mutual benefit. Making contacts with similar projects and establishing collaboration is considered beneficial for all. Open collaboration in mAKE is understood in a trans-disciplinary way, opening innovation processes to the wider public and allowing a new form of collaboration as intended in the co-design activities of the project.
- **Open source technology.** From a technology perspective, the project fosters the sharing maker infrastructure in makerspaces and innovation hubs. A main aim is to share the co-designed technological artefacts with the community. Business models and exploitation strategies are not based on locking down access to project results, but on providing added value through services.
- **Open access to scientific results.** From a scientific perspective, the consortium clearly favours open access to its scientific output, which is supported by several project members’ internal policies of supporting open access in general.
- **Open access to research data.** mAKE is part of a pilot action on open access to research data and is thus committed to providing access not only to project results and processes, but also to data collected during that process. Although mAKE is an innovation action according to the work programme definition and not a research action, some research related data will be collected, mainly from an evaluation perspective. Although the general policy of the mAKE project is to apply “open by default” to its research data, we have to handle privacy issues with special care. Legal rules on anonymity, as described above (chapter 6), are thus highly relevant and need to be

⁶ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_SPEECH-15-4532_de.htm

agreed upon with each of the participants. In case of doubt, data privacy of our participants always prevails over open data policy.

mAKE is part of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), a pilot action on open access to research data, which requires projects to define and execute a data management plan. This deliverable includes the open data management plan for mAKE. The open access strategy will be detailed in the following sections.

6.1 Open access strategy for publications and other artifacts

In line with the EC policy initiative on open access⁷, which refers to the practice of granting free Internet access to research articles, the project is committed to following a publication strategy considering a mix of both 'Green open access' (immediate or delayed open access that is provided through self-archiving) and 'Gold open access' (immediate open access that is provided by a publisher) as far as possible.

All deliverables labelled as “public” will be made accessible via the mAKE website. The publications stemming from the project work will also be made available on the website as far as it does not infringe the publishers’ rights as well as on the Zenodo platform.

All outcomes of the project, including design, protocols, databases, etc. that are labelled as “public” will be distributed under a specific free/open license, where the authors retain the authors’ rights but the users can redistribute the content freely. The following are a few relevant sources for deciding on the specific license for each outcome:

- Data:
 - A definition of Open Data:
 - Licenses:
- Software:
 - Free Software
 - The definition:
 - Licenses:
 - Open Source Software:
 - The definition:
 - Licenses:
- Reports, publications, media:
 - Creative Commons
 - Explanation:
 - Licenses:
 - Choose a license:

⁷<http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/index.cfm?fuseaction=public.topic&id=1294&lang=1>

- Sharing publications on the project website and via Zenodo

To summarise, the main open access points for mAkE data, publications, and innovation are:

- The project website: <https://makeafricaeu.org/>
- Zenodo: for depositing publications
- OpenAIRE for depositing research data (if applicable)
- Github/Gitlab
- AfricArXive

6.2 Open access and open data handling process

The internal procedures to grant open access to any publication, research data, or other innovation stemming from the mAkE project (e.g. technology), are following a lightweight structure, while respecting ethical issues at all times.

The main workflow starts at the WP level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures at all times during the data gathering and processing steps. The WP/working team members are also responsible for any data anonymization, if applicable. An agreement has to be reached within the team for making any outcome openly available; the final approval is done by the Project Management Board. Due to the nature of the project, the Data Management Plan may have to be revised during the course of project activities. As the co-design approach is a rather dynamic methodology it is not possible to clearly specify all data sources and collected outcomes from the beginning.

More details on all aspects related to data handling are provided in the Deliverable D8.2 Data Management Plan, which is due in Month 6.

7 Conclusions

This handbook describes the main procedures of the mAkE project to operate successfully and effectively in order to achieve high quality project results following a responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach. Open access, ethics, and engagement of all societal actors are amongst the key elements of the European RRI framework (European Union, 2012). mAkE is clearly committed to responding to societal challenges in a responsible way by itself and by the way the actions in the project are conducted.

While this handbook is provided in the form of a report and deliverable, it is a living document in the sense of being updated and challenged by the consortium in the course of the project. The processes described here are implemented in the daily work of the consortium and most of the elements (e.g. the forms for informed consent, data management plan, etc.) are separately available on the collaboration infrastructure such as Google Drive and Nextcloud.

The management reports will include updates on any crucial changes in the handbook as well as on the results of specific measures such as the SWOT analysis or any additional elements added to the project structure related to high quality responsible research.

8 References

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9 Annex I – Confidentiality Agreement and Data Exchange Format

Confidentiality Agreement

Research data shared between the researchers in the mAKE project may contain personal identifiable information (PII), the usage of which is protected by law. To comply with this law, usage, and sharing of data is restricted and it is essential that you follow the rules and guidelines described in the ethical guidelines defined for mAKE for collecting, processing, sharing, and storage of data.

In addition to this you are obliged to comply with the following terms:

- I will not share the participant data, collected by the project team, in which I am in receipt with any third parties, including the case study organisations, employers of the participants, or other members of the consortium of the mAKE project without explicit, written consent from the person(s) who provided the data.
- Where relevant, I will instruct the people for whom I have responsibility who have access to the data of the relevant ethical protocols and ensure that they follow the guidelines defined for the project, as listed below.
- I will delete the data at least _____ months after the project outcomes have been published (recommended time is 3 months).

Declaration: I hereby declare my consent with the rules outlined above:

Date:

Name & Organisation:

Signature:

List of persons in my organisation who have access to the data:

Data Exchange Form

As consortium partners in the mAKE consortium, we agree to share personal identifiable information (PII) of individuals and/or organisations as defined in the Confidentiality Agreement.

This data exchange form regulates the exchange between partners regarding sensitive data.

Researcher(s) responsible for the data (who collected the data originally)	
Type of data (e.g. interview recording, questionnaires, etc.)	
Sensitivity of data (describe briefly why this specific data is highly sensible)	
Consent form signed by all involved participants	
Storage location	
Person(s) who have access to the data	
Purpose of sharing	
Confidentiality agreement signed	
Data retention (timeframe for storing the shared data)	

Date:

Name & Organisation:

Signature:

10 Annex II – Checklist for Deliverables

1. Overall technical evaluation of the deliverable

1. Does the deliverable contain new, or value added information?
2. Are there any major technical errors, omissions, lack of necessary details?
3. How do the results compare with the state of the art and/or parallel activities?
4. What value does the document add to the project partners?

2. Executive summary

1. Are the following questions clearly asked and answered?
 1. Which problem(s) and key questions of interest to intended readers are addressed?
 2. What are the expected main benefits of this deliverable?
 3. What are the results contained in this deliverable?
 4. Who are the main consumers for this deliverable, e.g. who should read it?
 5. Why should I read the deliverable?
 6. Suggestions/recommendations for follow-up actions by project participants and/or by general public.
2. Is the length acceptable for the executive summary (e.g. approx. 2 pages)?

3. Introduction

1. Is the purpose of the document clearly stated?
2. Is the technical subject properly introduced?
3. If necessary, is there a guide to the reader (document structure, short description of chapters and relationships)?
4. If necessary, are there statements on technical assumption, readers' prerequisites, relationships with other documents or parallel activities?

4. The main part of the deliverable

1. Does it contain what was defined in the deliverable description in the DoA?
2. If something has been left out, have clear and valid reasons been given as to why?
3. Is the key part structured in a logical way?
4. Is the content appropriate for the intended audience? Does it only include essential information?
5. Does it duplicate or contradict standards or other on-going known initiatives? If yes, the affected standard or initiatives need to be identified.
6. Is the length acceptable (approx. 30 pages for main part)?

5. Conclusion

1. Are conclusions reached? Are they within the consortium perspective?
2. Are any necessary follow-up actions clearly indicated?
3. Are the conclusions consistent with the executive summary?
4. Should this Deliverable be
 1. Utilised by other projects?
 2. Released (in full or part) to the Associated Partner Network or to PES initiatives such as PES-to-PES dialogue?

6. Annexes (optional)

1. Are they complete in all parts?
2. Relevant for the content described in the deliverable?

11 Annex III Peer Review Template

Instructions: Peer reviewers should fill out all six sections in this template and send the completed template to the editor/main author on or before the specified due date.

1. Basic Information

- Deliverable Nr & Title:
- Main Author/Editor:
- Peer Reviewer (Institution, Person):
- Date of Receipt of Deliverable:
- Date of Sending out the completed peer review:

2. Length of the deliverable

- Is the length of the deliverable justified? – YES – NO
- If no, please specify by e.g. indicating parts that are superfluous, irrelevant, redundant, unspecific or would need more explanation?

3. Content

- Does the deliverable meet the objectives of the deliverable described in the respective Work Package Work Description? – YES – NO
 - If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.
- Is the content of the deliverable focused and presented in a precise and to-the-point manner? – YES – NO
 - If not, please indicate the parts where improvement is necessary.
- Does the deliverable require substantial revision or rewriting? – YES – NO
 - If yes, please give concrete suggestions how to improve the deliverable.

4. Major strengths

5. Major weaknesses

6. Review Summary

The current version of the deliverable is []:

- 1: applicable and ready to be submitted to the EC, if required;
- 2: applicable, but requires minor revisions;
- 3: inapplicable and requires substantial revisions.

Is it necessary for the revised deliverables to be reviewed again before submitting it to the EC (1:Yes, 2:No)? []

Other remarks:

